

D9.3 – Project website and social media accounts

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Executive Summary

This report is intended to provide an overview of the website, explaining the structure, the organisation of its contents and the further development. Furthermore, it also presents the social media accounts and the connection with the website.

The deliverable is about the set-up of website and social media; therefore it only describes how these products have been realised. It does not present any strategy of communication and dissemination, which is object of future deliverables.

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Abbreviation List

H&WB | Health and well-being

1. Introduction

The set-up of the project website and social media is part of the Task 9.2. Both website and social media are essential and complementary tools to achieve a successful outreach and dissemination of the project results.

The website is intended as the primary contact point and main access to VARCITIES project, both for a general audience and for specific target groups. For this reason, it is designed and built in a user-friendly way, essential but exhaustive, simple but professional at the same time. WP9 has strategically decided to implement first the website, and in a second moment to start using the social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn); the idea behind this decision is to provide social media users with a solid anchor to the project and a link to a tangible virtual place.

Both website and social media will be monitored starting from M4 (December 2020) by looking at the metrics and reporting the results. In this regard, the website is linked to google analytics (varcities.eu@gmail.com), while the social media already have different metrics and monitoring system. The goal is to monthly evaluate the performances and the growth of users and followers.

This report presents how the project website is designed and structured, starting from the original website map and then focusing on the homepage and the other internal pages. The last section is dedicated to social media.

The link to the website is: www.varcities.eu

2. Structure of the website

The website of a project such VARCITIES cannot be conceived as a static product, but it has to be a dynamic tool, able to accompany the implementation of the project through its various phases. For M3 the goal is to have an operative website which introduces the project in the most effective way, stimulating interest and curiosity, attracting visitors and fostering networking and contacts. Given that at this stage (M3) the project has not yet produced significant results, the structure of the website is intended to be essential but complete.

Furthermore, the Grant Agreement (p.131) already indicates some features of the website:

“The project website will be set up by ISOCARP by Month 3. The website will serve as the primary contact point for external stakeholders (media, scientists/researchers, industry, government and policy makers working on Nature Based Solutions, Smart Cities, Health and Wellbeing, climate and IoE and citizens) and will contain sections with a description of the VARCITIES project, ... the website will be designed with a simple and attractive layout ...”

Taking these indications into account, the website is built according to the following guidelines:

- User-friendly layout: fresh, clear design, essential structure, easy to navigate.
- Consistent design: the website follows the design of the project logo (fonts and color palette), and it is consistent through all the internal pages.
- Flexibility: the structure of the website is intended to be as flexible as possible, and to be built incrementally in parallel with the development of the project.

Figure 1: Website map

As highlighted from the original website map (Figure 1), the structure includes three main blocks.

- The first one is the section '**About Varcities**', which introduces the project, shortly presenting visions, objectives and impacts.
- The second block is the '**Pilot Cities**', presenting the eight municipalities and the pilot sites where the nature-based actions will be implemented.
- The third block is the '**News and Events**', an informative page where to update on the progress of the project and to inform visitors about relevant news, events etc.

Since the very beginning, it was decided to exclude from the initial set-up the block about '**Resources and Results**'. The idea is to create the page in the following weeks/months, following the rhythm of the project. Temporarily, significant resources will be included in the news page. The decision of having a small number of items (only 4) in the navigation menu is a conservative choice which allows to expand it in the next months (for example including direct link to the H&WB Platform).

2.1 'Homepage'

The homepage is designed following the principles of standard website homepages. It includes a header with the logo and the navigation menu, a cover image with a main title, a series of items which link to the internal pages, and an informative footer with the contacts.

Figure 2: Website homepage

The logo is located on the top-left of the page, slightly revised to better fit into the header. The navigation menu includes the links to the pages “About VARCITIES”, “Pilot Cities”, “News and Events”, “Contacts”. The cover image is taken from one of the pilot city, it gives a sense of freshness, dynamism and it is well combined with the project colors. The cover image is accompanied by the tagline “*Shaping the future of cities*”, which is neutral, but comprehensive and highlighting the future-oriented component of VARCITIES (Figure 2).

Right under the cover image and the main title, the pictogram icons of the logo are individually presented, accompanied by a caption. The colorful icons on white background give symmetry and dynamism to the homepage, completing the logo of VARCITIES and clearly presenting the fundamental components of the project.

Figure 3: website homepage | About VARCITIES

A short text about the project supported by an image, complete the presentation of the project and leads to the page 'About Varcities' (Figure 3). The goal is that a visitor is able to understand the nature and the soul of the project from a first look at the screen, without scrolling or clicking any link. The title of the paragraph is "*Green Cities are Healthier Cities*", which was the preferred version chosen by partners after a poll about the project tagline (this project tagline is also used for social media).

Figure 4: website homepage | Pilot Cities

The homepage continues by showcasing an overview of the geographical locations of the eight Pilot Cities, giving the possibility to discover more about these. This can be done by clicking on the button 'Pilot Cities' (which links to the page 'Pilot Cities') or by clicking on each city of the map to access specific Pilot (Figure 4). The map is intended to connect the Pilots and it is designed consistently with the visual identity of the project.

The page continues with a section dedicated to the News and Events (Figure 5). It includes the two most recent news and, on the right, it incorporates the most recent tweet from the VARCITIES account. The titles are consistent with the design of the logo and the news are followed by a very short introductory text.

Figure 5: website homepage | News & Events

After the news, the following section is the form which invites to subscribe to the project newsletter. It is meant to be as simple as possible and clearly visible on the homepage, in order to facilitate the number of subscriptions (Figure 6).

Figure 6: website homepage | Newsletter

The last part of the homepage is dedicated to the partners, shortly presenting the consortium. From an aesthetic point of view, it is preferable to have a slider and a transition of all the logos in one row (Figure 7). The button 'View all Partners' leads to the 'Contact Page', where all the logos of the partners are represented and grouped in the different categories.

Figure 7: website homepage | Partners

Lastly, the footer is divided in two parts (Figure 8). First, a series of squared images complete the homepage; these images can be replaced with Instagram posts in the following weeks-months, following a flexible layout, easy to adapt or replace. Second, the real footer includes the navigation menu and the contact links. In this regard, the email account contact@varcities.eu has been created, as well as the links to VARCITIES social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn).

Figure 8: website homepage | Footer

2.1.1 Planned further improvements

The homepage will be improved in the next weeks/months, adding the following changes:

- Add the page 'Resources/Results' to the navigation menu and create the internal page
- Replace the cover image and the title with possible new images and caption
- Integrate the link to the H&WB Platform and the Healthy Cities Helix.

2.2 'About'

This page is intended to describe the project, presenting in a concise but exhaustive way the vision, the objectives and the expected impacts of the project. The page includes some slider images from the pilots, the project logo and a caption with the full name of the project (Figure 9).

Figure 9: About VARCITIES | Vision

The page reserves a section also for the twin projects and other projects which could be involved in future collaboration and network activities (Figure 10). The last part of the page presents the VARCITIES team of colleagues working on the project, organised per partner, indicating the name and the email contact (Figure 11).

Figure 10: About VARCITIES | Networks

Figure 11: About VARCITIES | VARCITIES Team

2.2.1 Planned further improvements

The page is planned to be improved in the short term. In particular it will include more infographics with the objective to reduce the amount of text, improve the layout of the page

and the clarity of the contents.

2.3 ‘Pilot Cities’

The page is entirely dedicated to the presentation of the eight Pilot Cities (Figure 12). The page starts with a short introduction and the replication of the map already included in the homepage. Visitors can choose to click directly on the Pilot on the map (Figure 13), or they can click on the eight blocks below it (Figure 14). By clicking on the map, visitors will see a window opening, which includes a caption, a very short description of the Pilot and a representative image (Figure 13).

Each Pilot has its own page (Figure 15, Figure 16, Figure 17, Figure 18), with the same template. It includes two sliders, full screen images, six squared images and a text divided in three parts:

- The City: a short introduction of the City, mentioning geographical location, population, main attractions, challenges etc.
- The Pilot: a text introducing the pilot area of the project, explaining problems, objectives, and mentioning the actions financed by VARCITIES
- The Future City Vision: a short text presenting the vision of the city and how the solutions provided by VARCITIES are consistent with it.

Figure 12: Pilot Cities

Figure 13: Pilot Cities | example of Chania

Figure 14: Pilot Cities | City “blocks” and example of Dundalk

Figure 15: Pilot Cities | Gzira page

Figure 16: Pilot Cities | Chania page

Figure 17: Pilot Cities | Skellefteå page

Figure 18: Pilot Cities | Novo mesto page

Each page of the Pilot includes a section dedicated to local news, events and initiatives. A system of categorization will allow deciding systematically where to locale specific news.

2.3.1 Planned further improvements

The pages of the pilot cities will be upgraded following the results of the project, expanding the text and the number of images when relevant.

2.4 News and Events

The page is intended to be a straightforward access to the most recent news about VARCITIES. It is designed in a way that the news are ordered chronologically (Figure 19). The list of previous news can be accessed on the right of the page.

After the news, a calendar has been included and it works a simple visual tool to showcase future events, both from the consortium and from other relevant partners (Figure 20).

Temporarily (until the page 'Resource/Results' is not active), additional resources such as publications or links to external platforms could be added here.

Figure 19: News & Events

Figure 20: News & Events | Calendar

2.4.1 Planned further improvements

Future improvements will regard the layout of the calendar (i.e. categorization of the events) and a possible change in the layout of the news.

2.5 'Contact'

The 'Contact' page is meant to be as straightforward as possible and to facilitate the contact with VARCITIES (Figure 21). For this reason, a simple and essential form is created and users can send email to contact@varcities.com.

After the form, the partners are again presented. This time (and differently from the homepage) all the logos are present without any transition. Moreover, the partners are grouped in different categories according to their role inside the consortium (Figure 22). The following categories are created:

- Municipalities
- Universities and Research Centres
- Technical Experts and Technology Providers
- International partners

By clicking on a specific partner logo it is possible to reach the website of the partner.

Figure 21: Contact

Figure 22: Contact | Consortium organization

3. Social Media

Social media are essential tools for the communication and dissemination, and they cover a strategic importance in the Communication and Dissemination Plan. They will be regularly used for news, information and general outreach, and they will refer to the website as much as possible.

Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn are linked to the website and the icons are located in the footer of all the website pages. In addition, twitter feeds are incorporated in the homepage of the website, beside the news. Instagram deserves a particular mention: given its specificities, the homepage showcases a series of five squared blocks (Figure 23) which can be replaced by Instagram posts (the replacement will take place once five posts are completed).

The details of the social media accounts and the links are reported below:

- Facebook: **Varcities - Green Cities are Healthier Cities** | <https://www.facebook.com/VARCITIES> (Figure 24)
- Twitter: **VARCITIES** | <https://twitter.com/VARCITIES1> (Figure 25)
- LinkedIn: **Varcities - Green Cities are Healthier Cities** | <https://www.linkedin.com/company/varcities-green-cities-are-healthier-cities> (Figure 26)
- Instagram: **eu.varcities** | <https://www.instagram.com/eu.varcities/> (Figure 27)

Where possible (for Facebook and LinkedIn), the title was supplemented by the voted project tagline “Green Cities are Healthier Cities”.

Figure 23: Social media icons on the website and Instagram “blocks”

Figure 24: VARCITIES Facebook

Figure 25: VARCITIES Twitter

Figure 26: VARCITIES LinkedIn

Figure 27: VARCITIES Instagram

For each social media, the first post is dedicated to the presentation of the project, showing the logo and introducing to the website. Images taken from the Pilot Cities are regularly used as background images on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn; these will be regularly alternated in order to ensure the same visibility for all the eight Pilot Cities. As soon as the project advances, new infographics and images will be used.

Each social media account includes also a careful description of the project, selecting the most relevant hash-tags, keywords and thematic areas. Last but not least, contact information and link to the website are clearly indicated.

4. Conclusions

This report shows how the project website and social media have been set-up and activated. The task is successfully completed within M3, as indicated in the Grant Agreement. Potential future improvements have already been identified for the website, following the evolution of the project. The use of the social media accounts will be regulated according to the directives included in the Communication & Dissemination Plan, which will be realized within M7.

